

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE REGARDING ALCOHOLISM AND IT'S HAZARS AMONG THE GNM STUDENTS IN SELECTED NURSING COLLEGES WITH A VIEW TO DEVELOP AN INFORMATION BOOKLET**Mr. Sathish Thatikonda***

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ABSTRACT

Background Of The Study: Alcohol has a long history of use and misuse throughout recorded human history. Biblical, Egyptian and Babylonian sources record history of abuse and dependence on alcohol. In some ancient cultures alcohol was worshiped and in others its dependence was condemned. Excessive alcohol misuse and drunkenness were recognized as causing problems thousands of years ago. However, the defining of habitual drunkenness as it was then known as and its adverse consequences were not well established medically until the 18th century. World Health Organization's European Charter on Alcohol states that "all children and adolescents have the right to grow up in an environment protected from the negative consequences of alcohol dependence, to the extent possible, from the promotion of alcoholic beverages" As per Erikson's theory adolescents are in identity versus role confusion phase. They are still in teens and lacks maturity of thoughts and experience. She/he is not aware what is proper and improper and therefore is in danger of going on the wrong path. Youngsters like to experiment with a risky life without knowledge about long-term health dangers and risks. Alcohol marketing communications have a powerful effect on young people and come in many forms. These include traditional advertisements on television through ubiquitous ambient advertising to new media such as social network sites and viral campaigns. Wider implementation of policies is needed to save lives and reduce the health impact of harmful alcohol drinking, says a new report launched by WHO. Harmful use of alcohol results in the death of 2.5 million people annually, causes illness and injury to many more, and increasingly affects Younger generations and drinkers in developing countries. Globally, the world Health organisation has reported alcohol as one of the leading risk factors for morbidity and mortality world-wide, with approximately 1.8 million deaths annually, and representing a considerable economic problem for many communities around the world.

KEYWORDS: Alcohol marketing communications have a powerful effect on young people and come in many forms.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To see is the level of knowledge among GNM students regarding alcoholism and its hazards.
2. To prepare information booklets for students regarding alcoholism and its treatment.
3. To find out association between knowledge and selected demographic variables.

MATERIAL AND METHODS USED**Research approach**

In this study the investigator would like to assess the knowledge of GNM students regarding alcoholism and its hazards.

Setting

The study was conducted in selected Nursing colleges of the city.

Population

In this study GNM nursing Student are selected as study population from nursing colleges of the city.

Sampling and sampling technique

The sample comprises the 60 GNM nursing students of selected nursing colleges in the city under probability simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample.

Method and Technique

A Non-Experimental descriptive research design was used in this study. This study was conducted to "A descriptive study to assess the level of knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards among the GNM Students in selected nursing colleges with a view to develop an information pamphlet." Probability simple random sampling technique was used for a sample collection of 60 student i.e. GNM 1st, 2nd and 3rd year students studying in the Vaidyanath institute of nursing Parli. The main study conducted on 15/10/2022. Tool used for data collection consisted of structured Questionnaire (MCQ) to assess the level of knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards among GNM students.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Those students are available during study.
2. Those student are willing to participate in study.
3. Those students are age between 19-21 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Those students are having communicable disease.
2. Those students are learning in basic BSc nursing.

RESULT

Section I.

- ❖ Majority (45%) of the GNM students had age 19 years, whereas 26.7% of them had age 19-20 years, 20% of them had age 20-21 years and 8.3% of them had age above 21 years.
- ❖ Maximum (65%) of them were females and 35% of them were males. All of them had diploma.
- ❖ Majority (78.3%) of students income of family up to Rs. 50,000, and only 18.3% of students income of family between Rs.50000-70000, and 1.7% of them have an income between Rs.70000-100000 and only 1.7% of them have an income above Rs.100000.
- ❖ Maximum no (78.3%) of students were Hindu and 21.7% of them were Buddhists.
- ❖ Majority (51.7%) of families belongs to farmers, 13.3% of them have government job, 10% of them have private job, 25% of families were belongs to labours
- ❖ Majority (65%) of students were residing in rural area and only 35% of students were residing in urban area.
- ❖ Majority of students (68.3%) were staying with family. Whereas 23.3% of students were staying with friends, and (6.7%) of Students were staying in

a hostland only 1.7% of students staying with relatives.

Section II

Majority (76.7%) of students have average knowledge (Score 11-20) whereas (20%) of GNM students had poor knowledge (score 0-10), and only (3.3%) of them had good knowledge (score 21-30) regarding alcoholism and its hazards. 93.3% of the GNM students knew what is alcoholism. 20% of them knew the age group in which alcohol addiction is a major problem. 20% of them knew that deficiency of which vitamin causes alcoholism. 56.7% of them knew why people start consuming alcohol. 43.3% of them knew what long-term heavy alcohol consumption can cause. 40% of them knew the type of alcohol intoxication. 26.7% of them knew the risk of drinking alcohol. 51.7% of them knew the factors contributing to alcohol disorder. 58.3% of them knew the behaviours that may be a symptom of alcohol-use disorder. 50% of them knew the reason why students drink alcohol. 61.7% of them knew why the alcohol-use disorder is more dangerous in someone older than 65 years. 21.7% of them knew the key factor that influences blood alcohol concentration. 66.7% of them knew where alcohol was available. 46.7% of them knew cancer was caused by alcohol abuse in adults. 51.7% of them knew the high risk of alcohol. 23.3% of them knew the main metabolites of alcohol metabolism. 86.7% of them knew the effect of alcohol during pregnancy. 71.7% of them knew how long it takes for alcohol to affect the brain. 26.7% of them knew the symptoms of alcoholism. 28.3% of them knew the sign of alcohol poisoning. 16.7% of them knew the effect in the stomach to excessive consumption of alcohol. 23.3% of them knew what cirrhosis is cirrhosis. 30% of them knew the withdrawal symptoms of alcohol consumption. 45% of them knew how long it takes to have enough alcohol in blood to measure. 11.7% of them knew the inference at a blood alcohol concentration of 0.39%. 80% of them knew how much alcohol is safe per day. 13.3% of them knew the treatment that has been found to be most effective in treating addiction. 48.3% of them knew what can be done to drink less alcohol. 51.7% of them knew the legal age to buy alcohol in Maharashtra. 70% of them knew the preferred first-line medication for alcohol withdrawal.

CONCLUSION

The present study assesses the knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards within the genius students in selected colleges of the city. majority (76.7%) of students have average knowledge whereas 20% of students have a poor knowledge and only 3.3% of students have a good knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards.

Introduction

Alcoholism (also known as alcohol dependence syndrome) is defined as "a cluster of behavioral, cognitive, and physiological phenomena that develop

after repeated alcohol use and that typically include a strong desire to consume, difficulties in controlling its use, persisting in its use despite harmful consequences, a higher priority given to alcohol use than to other activities and obligations, increased tolerance, and sometimes a physical withdrawal state” (ICD-10).

Alcohol is a liquid of strong pungent taste, an inflammable intoxicating element in fermented or distilled liquor.

Alcoholism is now becoming a major problem of all the nations because it has given rise to the mortality rate. Approximately 2.5 million die each year from the harmful use of alcohol accounting for about 4% of all deaths in the world. More than half of these deaths occur from NCDs (Non-communicable diseases) including cancers, cardiovascular disease and liver cirrhosis. Alcohol consumption is the world's third largest risk factor for disease and disability; in middle-income countries, it is the greatest risk.

DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the discussion of the study with appropriate review of literature, statistical analysis and findings of the study based on the study of the objectives. Aim of present study is to Assess the level of knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards among the GNM students with a view to develop an information booklet.

Non experimental designs were used to study the samples of the study of 16 GNM students selected using probability simple random sampling technique to assess knowledge regarding alcoholism within the GNM students.

The consent of all GNM students obtained and structure and administrators conducted on the entire subject.

To objective of the study is to assist the knowledge regarding alcoholism in GNM students.

CONCLUSION

The present study assesses the knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards within the genius students in selected colleges of the city. 20% of students have a poor knowledge, 76.7% of students have average knowledge and 3.3 students have a good knowledge regarding alcoholism and its hazards.

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